

eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive Guidelines

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Abstract: The Humboldt Extension for ecological inventories mints the term `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` to describe how to treat counts of organisms when records from a single `dwc:Event` include multiple target categories. This document describes how to use that term.

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1 Introduction (non-normative)

This document elaborates upon the meaning and use of the term `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive`. Use of this term is necessary in order to describe how to treat counts of organisms (or any other organisms quantity) when records from a single `dwc:Event` (<http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/Event>) include multiple target categories (e.g., taxonomic ranks within a higher rank or different life stages for the same species). For example, a statement whether the least specific target category quantity is inclusive should be reported when an `dwc:Event` includes records reporting quantities that are associated with subcategories (e.g., subspecies) and records reporting quantities for more general categories (e.g., the species). In this example, the higher taxon rank (i.e., species) is the least specific category, because it is more general than the subspecies category nested below it. Species and subspecies are

just one example of a pair of category and subcategory. Other examples of subcategories are life stages (e.g., “adult”, “larva”, “egg”), and sexes.

1.1 Status of the content of this document

Sections 3 of this document is normative. The other sections are non-normative.

1.2 RFC 2119 key words

The key words "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are to be interpreted as described in RFC 2119.

1.3 Namespaces and terminology

The namespace `eco:` abbreviates <http://rs.tdwg.org/eco/terms/> and is used with terms minted for the Humboldt Extension for ecological inventories. `dwc:` abbreviates <http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/>, terms in the main Darwin Core vocabulary namespace. Words in code markup are term IRIs or literal values. The word "organisms" is used colloquially and is not used in the technical sense of the `dwc:Organism` class.

2 Rationale (non-normative)

The term `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` was introduced into the Humboldt Extension for ecological inventories late in development, after testing it with real-world cases (Sica et al., 2022). Testing revealed that the quantities of organisms stored in two major biodiversity databases — OBIS (OBIS, 2023) and eBird (Sullivan et al., 2014) — need to be treated differently in order to calculate the total quantity of organisms in the least specific category. In the specific case of data in the OBIS database, the information for a single `dwc:Event` can contain multiple records for a species, with one record for a species listing the quantity of individual organisms for the species without specifying any subcategory of life stage, and other records for the same species in the same `dwc:Event` listing quantities for different life stages (e.g., one record for adults and another record for juveniles). In this example the single `dwc:Event` will contain 3 records: one for the species without any life stage specified, one for adults of the species, and one for juveniles of the species. For the OBIS data, the quantity in the record for which no life stage is specified is the sum of three quantities: the number of juveniles, the number of adults, and the number of individuals that were not recorded as belonging to any specific life stage. In other words, when using OBIS data, the total quantity of individuals recorded for a species, across all life stages combined, has been

pre-calculated and stored in the database; unless the quantities of individuals within specific life stages are of interest, the information in the life stage subcategories can be ignored. The value of the term `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` in this case would be true - the least specific category (species without any life stage specified) already includes the counts of the more specific subcategories.

eBird stores information about quantities of organisms differently. For the example of a `dwc:Event` that contains separate records for subspecies and their parent species, the total number of individuals of the species needs to be calculated by the end user as the sum of the quantity reported for the species plus the quantities reported for the subspecies. In other words, the total quantity of organisms of each species has not been pre-calculated and must be derived by the end user. The value of the term `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` in this case would be false - the least specific category (species) does not include the counts of the more specific subcategories (subspecies).

In summary, the term `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` is required to inform the end user of whether they will need to derive the total quantity of organisms for the least specific category (e.g., for a species), or whether this total quantity has already been calculated prior to the data being entered into the database. Note that, if a dataset contains only simple targets that have no subcategories, the result of the term `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` being true or false is exactly the same - the count is the total in either case. Only in this circumstance does the term not strictly need to be populated. However, given that data records acquire a "life of their own" separate from their associated metadata when aggregated from multiple data sets, best practice is to include and populate the term `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive`.

3 Usage guidelines (normative)

The term `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` is defined as "The total detected quantity of organisms for a `dwc:Taxon` (including subsets thereof) in a `dwc:Event` is given explicitly in a single record (`dwc:organismQuantity` value) for that `dwc:Taxon`."

Values MUST be true and false. If true, the `dwc:organismQuantity` values for a `dwc:Taxon` in an `dwc:Event` is inclusive of all organisms of the `dwc:Taxon` (including more specific scopes such as different life stages or lower taxonomic ranks) and the total detected quantity of organisms for that `dwc:Taxon` in the `dwc:Event` MUST NOT be determined by summing the `dwc:organismQuantity` values for all records of the `dwc:Taxon` in the `dwc:Event`. Instead, the total detected quantity of organisms for the `dwc:Taxon` in an `dwc:Event` MUST be reported in a single record for the `dwc:Taxon` in the `dwc:Event`, with this record having no further specific scopes. In this case the sum of `dwc:organismQuantity` values for the reported subsets of the `dwc:Taxon` MUST NOT exceed the value of `dwc:organismQuantity` for the single record for the `dwc:Taxon` without subsets (i.e., the total). If false, the `dwc:organismQuantity` values for a `dwc:Taxon` in an `dwc:Event` MUST be added to get the total detected quantity of organisms for that `dwc:Taxon` in the `dwc:Event`.

4 Examples (non-normative)

4.1 Single `dwc:Taxon` example

As an example of the difference between true and false values for `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive`, suppose there are three records (see Table 1) with `dwc:organismQuantity` for a `dwc:Taxon` (`taxon_01`) for an `dwc:Event` (`event_01`). One record is for adults of the `dwc:Taxon` with `dwc:organismQuantity` = 1 and `dwc:organismQuantityType` = individuals, one record is for juveniles of the `dwc:Taxon` with `dwc:organismQuantity` = 2 and `dwc:organismQuantityType` = individuals, and one record is for the `dwc:Taxon` without specifying the life stage and with `dwc:organismQuantity` = 4 and `dwc:organismQuantityType` = individuals.

If `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` is true for `event_01`, then the total number of individuals of `taxon_01` for the `dwc:Event` is 4 (the least specific `dwc:Taxon` record — the one with no more specific scopes — includes all individuals of the `dwc:Taxon`). This means that there was 1 adult, 2 juveniles and 1 individual of `taxon_01` whose life stage was not recorded.

If `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` is false for `event_01`, then the total number of individuals of `taxon_01` for the `dwc:Event` is 7 (the least specific `dwc:Taxon` record - the one with no more specific scopes - does not include all individuals of the `dwc:Taxon`, rather, it is a separate category that must also be added to get the total). This means there was 1 adult, 2 juveniles and 4 individuals of `taxon_01` whose life stage was not recorded.

Table 1. Organism quantities in Occurrence records

occurrenceID	eventID	taxonID	lifeStage	organism Quantity	organism QuantityType
occ_01	event_01	taxon_01	adult	1	individual
occ_02	event_01	taxon_01	juvenile	2	individual
occ_03	event_01	taxon_01		4	individual

4.2 Nested taxa example

Suppose there are three records (see Table 2) with `dwc:organismQuantity` for three taxa (*Hirundo rustica* and two subspecies) for a `dwc:Event` (`event_01`). The record for the species has `dwc:organismQuantity` = 3 and `dwc:organismQuantityType` = individuals. The record for *H. r. rustica* has `dwc:organismQuantity` = 2 and `dwc:organismQuantityType` = individuals. The record for *H. r. gutturalis* has `dwc:organismQuantity` = 4 and `dwc:organismQuantityType` = individuals.

If `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` is true for `event_01`, then the total number of individuals of the species *H. rustica* for the `dwc:Event` is 3 (the least specific `dwc:Taxon` record includes all individuals of the `dwc:Taxon`). This means there were 2 *H. r. rustica*, 1 *H. r. gutturalis*, and no other *H. rustica* of any kind detected.

If `eco:isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive` is false for `event_01`, then the total number of individuals of the species *H. rustica* for the `dwc:Event` is 6 (the least specific `dwc:Taxon` record does not include all individuals of the `dwc:Taxon`). This means there were 2 *H. r. rustica*, 1 *H. r. gutturalis*, and 3 other *H. rustica* detected that were not identified to subspecies.

Table 2. Organism quantities in `dwc:Event` records

eventID	scientificName	organism Quantity	organism QuantityType
event_01	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	3	individual
event_01	<i>Hirundo rustica rustica</i>	2	individual
event_01	<i>Hirundo rustica gutturalis</i>	1	individual

5 References

OBIS (2023) Ocean Biodiversity Information System. Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO. <https://www.obis.org/>.

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